

Integrating Artificial Intelligence to Enhance Clinical Documentation, Real-Time Auditing, and Decision-Making in a Tertiary Care Hospital: A Comparative Audit Study

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Abstract: This study explores how artificial intelligence (AI) can enhance healthcare documentation, auditing, and decision-making amid growing system complexity and patient demands. The discussion outlines AI's potential to improve legibility, support real-time decision-making, and automate tasks such as dosage adjustment and safety alerts. AI could also shift audits from retrospective reviews to proactive, real-time monitoring.

Keywords: Artificial Intelligence (AI), real-time auditing, decision-making, record-keeping

1 Introduction

Artificial Intelligence (AI) is progressively reshaping the healthcare industry by simulating human cognitive functions and streamlining complex processes. As the volume of clinical data increases and the demand for high-quality, patient-centered care intensifies, healthcare systems are under pressure to adopt innovative solutions [1]. Documentation, auditing, and clinical decision-making are among the core operational domains that remain heavily reliant on manual input, often resulting in delays, errors, and inconsistencies [2]. These inefficiencies are particularly evident in high-pressure environments such as inpatient wards, where time-sensitive decisions and accurate record-keeping are critical.

This study aims to evaluate current clinical documentation practices and identify how AI integration could enhance efficiency, reduce human error, and support timely clinical interventions. Through two distinct audits conducted at a tertiary care hospital in Cork, Ireland—one involving traditional manual methods and the other using electronic tool—we assess gaps in compliance with standards such as those established by the Joint Commission International (JCI). In addition, insights from frontline healthcare workers were gathered to explore perceptions of current challenges and receptivity to AI-driven tools.

2 Method:

A comparative observational study design was employed, comprising two separate audits performed at Bon Secours Hospital, Cork. The first audit assessed 127 inpatient records using an electronic MEG tool. It is a digital audit baseline for clinical documentation completeness and compliance. While it offers standardized data collection and reporting, it lacks the real-time feedback, natural language understanding, and intelligent recommendations enabled by AI-based systems introduced in the intervention phase. The second audit analysed 81 inpatient records documented through traditional paper-pen method. Both audits evaluated clinical documentation quality, focusing on:

- VTE (Venous Thromboembolism) risk assessment completion and appropriateness of prescription
- Compliance with institutional and JCI standards regarding clinical note-taking
- Documentation reliability, legibility, and completeness, including key identifiers such as patient unique ID, date, time, physician signature, IMC number, and consultant stamp

Additionally, a structured questionnaire was developed and distributed to randomly selected Senior House Officers (SHOs), registrars, and interns. The questionnaire contained closed-ended questions assessing time spent on documentation, quality of notes, accessibility, and perceptions of AI integration. It is a part of quality improvement audits.

Audit data were manually reviewed and analysed to identify systemic inefficiencies and documentation errors. Common themes in the survey responses were coded to identify major challenges and clinician needs that AI could address.

3 Results:

3.1 – Electronic Records with Manual Validation

The first audit, comprising 127 inpatient records, was conducted over a two-week period. All data were entered into an electronic system for analysis. The audit found that:

- **VTE assessments** were completed in a timely manner in 81% of cases.
- **Prescription appropriateness** was achieved in 100% of reviewed records in all the 81% cases. While remaining 19% were not assessed leaving at high risk of developing Deep venous thrombosis and Pulmonary embolism, increasing hospital mortality rate.

However, manual drug chart entries posed significant risks, including transcription errors and delayed administration, largely attributed to high patient load and insufficient staffing.

3.2 – Manual Documentation

The second audit, evaluating 81 records, was conducted over a 3–4 week period. Key findings included:

- Patient identifiers such as unique ID numbers were missing in 21%.
- IMC registration numbers were frequently missing or incomplete, with 30% of notes lacking junior doctor’s designation or IMC number and 60% Consultant’s designation or IMC number.
- Chronological inconsistencies were observed in 10-20% of notes due to the absence of proper timestamps and also due to improper filing.
- Only 46% of records included a recorded time alongside the date.

Discharge summaries were produced electronically but required manual input, consuming an average of 20 minutes per case. This process was inefficient and burdensome, especially during peak clinical hours.

Qualitative review revealed that critical issues in record-keeping included difficult handwriting, lack of standardized format, and variability in documentation practices across different clinicians. This inconsistency hindered continuity of care and increased the risk of clinical oversight.

3.3 Clinician Survey Results:

Responses revealed the following trends:

- **80%** reported difficulty locating patient notes due to disorganized paper records and poor chart maintenance, particularly for long-stay patients.
- **70%** indicated that documentation delayed ward rounds due to difference in writing speed leading to scribbling of words.
- Handwriting interpretation delays were commonly reported, requiring nurses or doctors to clarify or re-confirm treatment plans.
- **Multiple consultants allowed junior staff to retrospectively enter notes**, often leading to omissions due to memory constraints.

Clinicians noted that repetitive documentation tasks could be streamlined by AI tools capable of auto-generating templates, pre-filling discharge summaries, and standardizing inputs. Most respondents expressed support for AI-based systems to reduce administrative workload, enhance note accuracy, and improve clinical workflow.

4 Discussion:

The findings of this study highlight substantial inefficiencies in current documentation and auditing practices, both in traditional and semi-digital environments. Manual note-taking, even when supplemented by electronic tools, remains error-prone, time-

consuming, and inconsistent. These limitations directly impact clinical decision-making, patient safety, and physician well-being.

This study evaluates the impact of digitization on clinical documentation quality and real-time auditing through the implementation of the MEG tool, a non-AI digital audit system. The data highlight existing challenges and improvements achieved over traditional paper-based methods. While this study does not directly implement AI models, it proposes the future integration of AI technologies—such as natural language processing (NLP) and large language models, to further enhance documentation accuracy, medication safety, and clinical decision support. The findings validate that digitization provides a crucial foundation for future AI adoption, and early experimental initiatives suggest promising directions for improving healthcare quality.

AI tools like GPT-4 (via OpenAI and Microsoft Azure) have demonstrated the capacity to enhance clinical workflows in other settings by summarizing patient visits, automating chart reviews, and enabling real-time documentation based on doctor-patient conversations. Similarly, NLP models have been applied in various healthcare contexts to assist in drafting discharge summaries and flagging incomplete or inconsistent documentation. Importantly, these systems are designed to function with clinicians in the loop, serving as supportive tools to reduce documentation burden and enhance care delivery [5].

While digitization has improved document formatting and reduced manual errors, AI components—such as real-time NLP auditing and auto-suggestion systems—are being considered in future workflows to further strengthen documentation completeness and decision-making. For instance, NLP frameworks like **spaCy** can potentially be used to extract and validate documentation elements such as clinician registration numbers and signatures. In parallel, models like **fine-tuned BERT** are reported in literature for their ability to flag incomplete discharge summaries and ensure content consistency [6]. These AI applications, though not yet implemented in the study setting, represent viable future directions based on emerging global practices.

In the domain of **medication safety**, the NLP model can enable real-time dose adjustments based on clinical parameters such as weight and glomerular filtration rate (GFR), flagging potential drug interactions, and support deprescribing without reliance on external applications. Furthermore, AI-enabled decision support systems can assist in prioritizing tasks—such as early warning score alerts or uncompleted VTE assessments—within 24 hours of patient admission.

Moreover, it can also revolutionize **clinical auditing**, shifting from retrospective reviews to real-time surveillance. This enables continuous quality improvement, automatic identification of non-compliance with protocols, and generation of audit-ready reports without human intervention [3].

However, implementation of AI in clinical settings is not without challenges. Concerns around **data privacy**, **user authentication**, and **GDPR compliance** must be

addressed through robust encryption, audit trails, and secure login systems [4]. Training programs will be essential. Ethical oversight must also guide decision-making algorithms to prevent over-reliance on automated outputs.

The weakness and limitation of this paper is that the proposed models are not actual implemented around the hospital. It can be considered as a pilot for testing purposes before been fully introduced across the entire hospital.

5 Conclusion:

This study demonstrates the pressing need for modernization in clinical documentation and auditing processes. AI holds considerable promise for improving accuracy, efficiency, and safety in healthcare delivery. By integrating AI into electronic health records (EHR), hospitals can enhance compliance, streamline clinical workflows, reduce clinician burnout, and ultimately deliver more timely, patient-centered care.

Future studies should explore implementation strategies, cost-effectiveness, and long-term outcomes of AI-enabled documentation tools. Engagement from clinicians, IT professionals, and regulatory bodies will be key to successful adoption and sustainability of these technologies.

Disclosure of Interests. There are no competing interests.

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